

Project branding, website design & social media account

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PilotSTRATEGY (H2020- Topic LC-SC3-NZE-6-2020 - RIA)

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www.pilotstrategy.eu

1 Document History

Location

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This document requires the following approvals:

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2 Executive summary

The PilotSTRATEGY branding, website and social media accounts are essential communication tools, which define the project image and provide a hub for all project details, activities and results, and more information about geological CO₂ storage sites in industrial regions of Southern and Eastern Europe for the purpose of large-scale carbon capture and storage (CCS) development.

This document outlines the processes that were followed from establishing the branding & website brief through to developing the project website.

The website will be made public on 31st of August 2021. The web address will be as follows:
<http://www.pilotstrategy.eu>

Logo:

Logo with branding/visual identity:

Website home page:

The PilotSTRATEGY project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101022664

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3 Project Brief (for design agencies)

This section contains the project brief sent to web design agencies, containing detailed requirements for the brand ID, logo design, and website development.

3.1 Summary of work required

SCCS is a partner in a new European project called PilotSTRATEGY, which starts in May 2021 and runs for five years. We would like to invite you to quote for the design and development of the items listed below. For more details, see the subsequent sections of this document.

- Design of Brand ID
 - Logo, colour palette and branding guidelines
 - Design of project templates (Word documents, PowerPoint slide pack, A1/A0 poster)
 - 3x Infographics
 - Design of a project summary brochure and project poster
 - Design of a MailChimp template for newsletters
- Design and development of project Website (including hosting and support for the five years of the project duration + two additional years)

3.2 Project Summary

The PilotSTRATEGY project focuses on the appraisal and development of geological CO₂ storage in five industrial regions in Southern and Eastern Europe, and detailed studies of deep saline aquifers (DSAs) in the Paris Basin (France), Lusitanian Basin (Portugal) and Ebro Basin (Spain). The project results will allow final investment decisions to be made and for storage permitting and project approval to be obtained in these three regions. In West Macedonia (Greece) and Upper Silesia (Poland), the project will increase understanding of storage resources and enable the development of CO₂ storage resources.

The PilotSTRATEGY website will be a key part of the project's communication and dissemination activities, including stakeholder engagement and knowledge exchange.

3.3 Brand ID Requirements

We require the design of the branding that will define the project identity. This must include more than one project Logo concept, and the final logo must be made available in colour, mono, and small icon (for use in social media, favicon, etc) versions (EPS, JPG, PNG), along with a branding guidelines document. Details of preferences (colours, shapes, imagery) will be provided based on a questionnaire sent to project partners. In addition, we would like the proposal to include quotes for the following:

- 2x Word document templates – one for reports, one for minutes (using project branding, header/footer, and paragraph styles)
- PowerPoint document template (using project branding, and including master slides for title, plain text, bullets, thank you, and acknowledgements)

- A1/A0 project poster template (using project branding, and including all project partner logos)
- 3x Infographics to be defined at a later stage - [Example](#)
- Design of a project summary brochure - [Example](#)
- Design of a MailChimp template for newsletters - [Example](#)

3.4 Website Requirements

3.4.1 Content types

Based on our requirements, the PilotSTRATEGY website would require the following content types:

- Text, images, and graphics
- Links to open/download documents/reports/outputs (most likely PDF) - [Example](#)
- Links to external pages
- Links to social media (Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube)
- Embedded Twitter feed
- Embedded YouTube videos - [Example](#)
- Map - [Example](#)
- Newsletter sign-up option (to integrate with MailChimp)
- Search options - [Example](#)
- Filter options - [Example](#)
- Contact form - [Example](#)

In addition, a password-protected area may be required (please quote separately)

3.4.2 Website Pages

The PilotSTRATEGY website structure will be defined at a later stage, but we envision it will require the following pages:

- Home Page
- About the Project
- Project Partners
- Advisory Board
- Industry Club
- Project Outputs
- News
- Events (incl date and time fields)
- Contact Us
- Funding acknowledgements
- Cookies Policy
- Privacy Policy
- Accessibility Statement

Additional pages to be determined/decided later (please quote separately)

- Glossary page - [Example](#)
- Useful links page - [Example](#)

3.4.3 Technical Specifications

- Domain: the domain will be procured by SCCS, relevant DNS and technical information for launch will be provided
- Upon setup of the website, we require user accounts to be set up so that SCCS can access the back end to:
 - Create pages and assign it to menus
 - Edit pages
 - Upload/Update pictures (with option for credit)
 - Embed Videos
 - Add new users
 - Redirect pages
- Tracking (Website statistics): Google analytics plugin required
- Accessibility: The website must comply with the UOE [web accessibility policy](#)
- Security: we require website security, firewall, and backups to be provided and looked after by you.
- Hosting: we require hosting for the duration of the project (five years). Additional hosting for a further two years may be required.
- Data: the website must be GDPR compliant.

4 Website Questionnaire

This section contains a summary of a questionnaire sent to project partners to provide information to define the overall use and feel of the project image, identity and website. These results determine the main goals for the website, outline specific sections required, and inform preferences for colours, and imagery for branding. The results informed the branding and website design, and the website build process.

1. What are the primary and secondary goals of the website?

Publicity/External visibility of the project with informative objectives; communication and dissemination of progress and outputs; provide information to local community, stakeholders and the consortium; provide regions with information about CCUS and the ongoing discussion in their areas; raise awareness on the financial gains of such projects; organise and publicise dissemination events, such as webinars; present the main objectives of the project and the motivations for the importance of the study and identification of sites with geological storage capacity of CO₂

2. What are the long-term goals of the website?

Maintain repository of publications, reports and knowledge gained; to keep the results and data accessible; provide information for policymakers; to provide and display tangible results from our research and outputs, produce proofs of concept as gained throughout the project life, also take into account social acceptance and concerns at regional level

3. Who is our target audience?

Local community, policy-makers, researchers, companies, project partners, stakeholders, general public, environmental NGOs, media, large industries with high CO₂ emissions. Engagement of administrations and enterprises with investment, decision and regulatory capabilities will be key.

4. What are their areas of interest and/or concern?

Our results on CCUS storage in the regions; results that can be used for their own activities; technical feasibility; data sharing; trust in the technology; social acceptance; CO₂ storage sites in Europe, Geological characterization of storage sites; design of appraisal/injector well; get answers to questions about future plans for their regions; safety operations; environmental impact; economic impact, regulatory frameworks; deeper understanding of the topic.

5. List the typical tasks visitors might perform on the website.

Access and download reports, publications and other outputs; check the organisations linked to the project; read general descriptions, understand HSE aspects of the project, discover the goals of the project and CCS; follow news, subscribe to newsletter, contact the project, find out/register to events; locate projects on a map, find out about project timelines and goals.

6. What adjectives can be used to describe the way the website should be perceived by the targeted audience?

Easy to use, intuitive, clear, informative, attractive, simple, reachable, scientific, societal, environmentally aware, friendly, stimulating, transparent, thorough, unbiased, open, comprehensive, well-structured, appealing, educational, practical, objective, forward-looking, complete.

7. What do you want your audience(s) to do as a result of visiting the website?

Have the information they were looking for; cite the publications, use the results, share; feel educated on the topic, willing to participate/invest; accept CCUS as a climate change solution; contact local members of the consortium for more info; provide feedback; subscribe to our newsletter, and engage with the project; feel encouraged to find out more about the topic after visiting the website.

8. What is the overall message we are trying to convey?

We are preparing a pilot for CO₂ geological storage in the region; the research process is rigorous, sound and that the results are trustworthy and useful; it is a proven concept that works; CO₂ pilot sites are a necessary step between R&D and industrial scale to improve knowledge and technologies.

9. How should we measure the success of the website?

Number of visitors, number of downloads, shares and followers on social media, number of subscribers to our newsletter, number of people contacting the project through the website, number of people registering to events, number of citations.

10. Do you have any suggestions for a project tagline? (A concise phrase that appropriately describes the project and its aims)

- Assessing the viability and acceptability of carbon storage.

- Characterizing geological resources in promising regions, setting up new CO2 storage pilots
- Taking the next steps
- Developing regional pilots for accelerating CCS action at large scale
- Ready for CO2 storage: detailed studies and design for doing a reality CCUS in South of Europe

11. What colours do you think best convey the project and its aims? (in order of popularity)

Green, blue, yellow, brown, light blue, white. Additional comments: similar to [EU green deal colours](#): drawing of the colours of nature (green, blue, brown); European union yellow and blue

What visual elements, shapes or objects might convey the project and its aims?

Rocks; mountains; object with movement showing acceleration; image of a team or community; something resembling underground systems; arrows and targets to show that we are pursuing objectives and aims and how to achieve them; the image of a map to represent regions.

Have you seen any styles of website that would be suitable for PilotSTRATEGY? Please supply web links

<https://b-watersmart.eu/>

<https://scarbo-h2020.eu/>

<https://www.quidnetenergy.com/>

<https://www.eera-set.eu/>

<https://www.carbfix.com/>

12. In addition to standard sections/pages (about the project, funding details, project partners, project outputs, news, events, contact us, privacy/accessibility/cookies policies, social media links), what others should we include?

In order of preference (most popular to least popular by # of votes)

- CCUS information specific to project focus – 15
- Map – 14
- Useful links – 14
- Search function – 12
- Advisory Board / Industry Club – 11
- Glossary – 10
- Password-protected area – 6
- Other
- FAQs debunking common misconceptions – 1
- Forum of discussion – 1
- Explanatory videos - 1

6 Project Logo

6.1 Logo Development

This section outlines the iterative process of developing the project logo together with the project partners. Based on ideas suggested during the website questionnaire, two logo concepts were designed and presented to project partners during the kick-off meeting

option 1

option 2

Taking into consideration comments and feedback about the best of both concepts, a third option was designed

option 3 stacked

option 3 wide

6.2 Final Logo

Main logo

Greyscale logo

Mono logo

Social Media icon

7 Brand ID

Along with the development of the project logo, a range of branding elements were also designed to define the image of the PilotSTRATEGY project.

7.1 Branding image

7.2 Graphic elements

7.2.1 Homepage “hero” graphic showing iterative process of design

Initial concepts

Additional suggested changes to option 3

Final version

7.2.2 Additional branding graphics

Objectives and Outcomes

Results

8 Website Development

8.1 Site Overview and Content Type

The website structure was created based on the feedback we received in response to our online questionnaire to define the following site overview.

8.1.1 Site Overview

We envision the PilotSTRATEGY website as having the following web pages. The first tier in **bold** would be in the main menu, second tier in *italics* would be a submenu, third tier (where relevant) is a brief description of the content. Pages marked with a * will launch at a later stage (expected around the 6-month review)

Homepage to include static map with interactive popups that take you to each region page

- **About the project**
 - *Overview*
 - WP1 – WP7
- **Objectives & Outcomes**
 - Timeline of key dates (may be a graphic on the Objectives page)
- **Explore the regions**
 - Individual region pages
 - Result*
 - FAQs / Debunking myths/Misconceptions* – Up to 6 Explanatory Videos
 - Useful Links*
 - Glossary*
- **CCUS Context (working title) ***
- **Partners**
 - Project Partners
 - Grid with logos and filters (most likely by WP, country, and type)
 - Advisory Board*
 - Grid with logos (filter requirement TBD)
 - Industry Club*
 - Grid with logos (filter requirement TBD)
- **News**
 - News page
 - Individual News posts (include visual tag to show if it's news, blog, video, media, report)
 - Newsletter archive*
 - List of past newsletters listed
- **Events**
 - *Event page* (show date and time visible in event list)
 - Individual event
- **Contact Us**
 - Contact form, contact details and newsletter sign-up

In addition, the website will contain the follow pages at the footer:

- Funding
- Privacy Policy
- Cookies Policy
- Accessibility statement

8.1.2 Content Types

Based on the above pages, and other similar sites, we envision the following content types to be required for the website:

- Text
- Images
- Graphics
- Pop-up interactive Map (showing location of companies involved in project) (similar to <https://www.strategyccus.eu/about-project/regions>)
- Links to open/download documents/reports (most likely PDF)
- Links to external pages
- Links to social media (Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube)
- Embedded Twitter feed
- Embedded YouTube videos
- Search options
- Contact form
- Newsletter sign-up option (from MailChimp)
- Past Newsletters archive (from MailChimp) (similar to <https://actacorn.eu/news-and-events/past-newsletters>)

8.2 Website Structure and Wireframes

This section outlines the website structure developed from the *site overview and content types* document and presents examples of page wireframes.

8.2.1 Website structure

8.2.2 Home Page Wireframe

8.2.3 Explore the Regions Wireframe

8.3 Source Materials

Content was taken from bid documents, and drafted in consultation with the project coordinator and project partners.

- Sourcing/drafting text content (Virginia Marsh).
- Timeline of Key Events (Richard Lo Bianco)
- Partner logos from project partners and organisations (Romain Viguiet)

8.4 Hi-fi Mock-ups

Home page

About the Project

[Home](#) > [About the Project](#)

About the Project

The PilotSTRATEGY project is investigating geological CO₂ storage sites in industrial regions of Southern and Eastern Europe for the purpose of large-scale carbon capture, utilisation and storage (CCUS) development.

Work Packages

WP2 Geo-characterisation Explore WP2	
WP4 Pilot Development Explore WP4	
WP6 Social Acceptance Explore WP6	
WP7 Communication & Impact Explore WP7	

Explore the Regions

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[Explore the Regions](#)

Objectives & Outcomes

Carbon capture, utilisation and storage (CCUS) has a crucial role in Europe's climate ambitions, particularly for the future viability of industrialised regions. This will depend on the right amount of geological CO₂ storage becoming available in the [2020s], 2030s and beyond.

[Explore Objectives & Outcomes](#)

Results

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Aenean euismod bibendum laoreet. Proin gravida dolor sit amet lacus accumsan et viverra justo commodo. Proin sodales pulvinar sic tempor. Sociis natoque penatibus et magnis dis parturient montes, nascetur ridiculus mus. Nam fermentum, nulla luctus pharetra.

[Explore Results](#)

FAQs
[Explore FAQs](#)

Useful Links
[Explore Useful Links](#)

Glossary
[Explore Glossary](#)

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Work Packages

Management

Overall coordination and management of the project internally and externally

- Day-to-day project management
- Project Consortium Agreement monitoring
- Risk management and quality control

[Explore WP1](#)

Simulation

Assessment of site storage capacity and integrity

- Storage capacity and injection strategy
- CO₂ fate in the long term
- Integrity of near wellbore caprock and fault/fractures

Safety

Ensuring proposed pilots meet the best safety and performance standards

- Ensure no significant risk of leakage or damage to human health/environment
- Methodological framework and guidance
- Recommendations for pilot implementation

Communication & Impact

Increasing the visibility and impact of the project

- Communicate vision and findings
- Deliver dissemination activities
- Project data and impact management

Geo-characterisation

Assembling, acquiring and interpreting geological data

- Geological modelling of pilot sites (Ebro, Lusitanian and Orleans-Paris Basins)
- Bespoke data acquisition and usage for each pilot region
- Re-interpret data for secondary sites (Upper Silesia, West Macedonia)

Pilot Development

Development concepts for proposed pilots (Ebro, Lusitanian and Orleans-Paris Basins)

- Information to enable decision on viability of each pilot
- Pilot design and investment proposal
- Robust project life-cycle

Social Acceptance

Investigating societal acceptance and public engagement

- Understand public attitudes and needs
- Build community and stakeholder participation
- Develop public engagement recommendations

[← Back to About the Project](#)

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9 Other

9.1 Test plan

Upon completion of the development stage, the developers (Starbit) undertook compatibility testing on a range of devices. Starbit will also provide remote access to the development version so that SCCS could carry out parallel testing. Any fixes were then applied to the development version of the site for final approval. Once approved, the site will be transferred to the live hosting environment. Starbit will thereafter provide 20 working days of support to cover any minor issues that are subsequently discovered.

9.2 User feedback survey

A user feedback survey, in line with agreed project timelines, will be distributed among WP Leads/partners. The survey is likely to cover:

- Meeting the brief
- Ease of use
- Time taken to find information
- Aesthetics
- Comprehensibility

9.3 Analytics

Analytics will be collated, in line with agreed project timelines. This is likely to cover metrics such as:

- Most visited pages
- Popular pages
- Website traffic

10 Social media account

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/pilotstrategy/>

PilotSTRATEGY
Geological CO₂ storage to support carbon capture, utilisation & storage (CCUS) in Europe. Funded by H020 programme.
Research · 15 followers

✓ Following More

Home About Posts Jobs People

About

The PilotSTRATEGY project focuses on the appraisal and development of geological CO₂ storage in five industrial regions in Southern and Eastern Europe.

[see more](#)

[See all details](#)

YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCE1NzmSFJ1e4fEirs_Dg1Hg

YouTube

Search

Home Explore Subscriptions Library History Your videos Watch later Liked videos

SUBSCRIPTIONS

SCCS (Scottish Carb...)

Japania

PilotSTRATEGY

SUBSCRIBE

HOME VIDEOS PLAYLISTS CHANNELS DISCUSSION ABOUT

Twitter: @PilotSTRATEGY

Explore

⚙ Settings

11 Conclusion

This document records the development of the brand ID, logo, and the initial version of the website and related tasks and list the project's social media accounts. The website will be updated throughout the project to disseminate the project outcomes and results as they are generated. The final version of the website, which will act as a legacy to the project, will be made public at the end of the project.

